

Structural and Operational Challenges in Agricultural Export Business and the Role of Government Policies.

Dr. Sonali R. Kshirsagar¹ & Mr. Sandip P. Ghumare²

¹Asst. Professor Dept. Of Management Science,

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Chh. Sambhajinagar.

²Research Scholar, Ph.D. Dept. Of Management Science,

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Chh. Sambhajinagar.

Corresponding Author – Dr. Sonali R. Kshirsagar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18516324

Abstract:

Agri exporters face several structural and operational challenges, especially in regions like Marathwada. These challenges include inadequate infrastructure, shortage of skilled manpower, limited technology use, lack of market information, and difficulties in meeting international quality standards. Exporters also experience problems due to complex procedures, frequent policy changes. This study examines the key challenges faced by agricultural export businesses in the Marathwada region and evaluates the role of government policies in supporting exporters. The study is based on primary data collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using percentage analysis and the Chi-square test. The findings show that while government support exists, procedural and operational issues continue to limit export performance. The study suggests that simplifying procedures, improving infrastructure, and increasing exporter awareness can help strengthen agricultural exports.

Keywords: Agricultural Exports, Structural Challenges, Operational Challenges, Government Policies, Export Barriers, Export Procedures, International Marketing, Marathwada Region

Introduction:

International trade plays a crucial role in the economic development of a country, particularly for developing economies like India. Agricultural exports play a vital role in India's foreign trade by supporting income generation and economic stability. However, the process of exporting agricultural products involves several structural and operational difficulties that affect the performance of exporters. Agricultural exporters in regions like Marathwada face several challenges due to inadequate infrastructure, limited facilities, lack of education, finance, technical and managerial skills, and frequent policy changes, along with complex legal, tax, and procedural requirements that increase uncertainty and operational difficulties, especially

for small exporters. Internal challenges include shortage of skilled manpower, limited market information, and weak marketing capabilities, while external challenges stem from regulatory complexities, government procedures, and changing international markets, varying by exporters' size, experience, and preparedness. Government policies significantly influence the export environment, but exporters often face difficulties in accessing benefits due to procedural delays, low awareness, and implementation gaps. Therefore, this study examines the structural and operational challenges of agricultural exporters in the Marathwada region and assesses the effectiveness of government policies in addressing these issues to improve policy

implementation and support mechanisms for agricultural exporters.

Review of Literature:

Kabra⁶ (1983) The study highlights the importance of agricultural exports for India's earnings but warns that overdependence on them can shift farmers away from food crops. It stresses the need to balance export growth with domestic food needs. Deb² (1976) 76 The study analyzed India's export problems across different commodities and regions and found that slow export growth is mainly due to limited export surplus, uncompetitive prices, inadequate incentives and support, transportation and shipping issues, and weak marketing. It concluded that addressing these challenges is essential to improve India's export performance. Gupta⁵ (1975) 75 The study critically reviewed agricultural marketing practices in India and identified several key problems in the existing system. It suggested that developing a more efficient and well-organized marketing system would help improve overall marketing standards in the country. Jasdanwala³ (1965) 68 The study emphasizes the need for a well-organized and efficient marketing system to strengthen India's agricultural sector. It highlights the importance of improving market information, transport, storage, regulated markets, standardization, and credit facilities, and suggests that better cropping patterns and marketing practices are essential for overcoming existing constraints and supporting cash crop producers.

Ahmed et al¹ (2004) The study analyzed export barriers faced by Lebanese manufacturers using survey data from 61 firms and applied statistical tools such as t-tests and ANOVA. It found that key challenges included limited government support, strong foreign competition, the need to adjust pricing and promotion strategies, high foreign tariffs, and restricted access to finance for

international expansion. Goyal S K et al⁴ (2000) 45 The study found that India's agricultural exports declined over time, with traditional products losing importance, while items like marine products, rice, and fruits gained importance in the 1990s. Although India's global share remained low, it improved after liberalization, showing the need for innovation, efficient delivery, and consistent quality at competitive prices. Ali Lagzi and Thimmarayappa⁷ R10 (2012) 28 The study highlighted India's strong potential in processed food exports, especially fruits and vegetables, supported by its diverse climate and geography. Using secondary data, it noted growing export opportunities in regions such as the Middle East, Europe, Japan, and Southeast Asia, and emphasized that proactive policies and strategic initiatives are needed to strengthen exports and benefit farmers, consumers, and businesses.

Objectives Of The Study:

The main objective is to study the challenges of Agricultural Export business in Marathwada region. To identify, and analyze the perceived export barriers faced by the exporting firms and to answer what are the main barriers, and effectiveness of Government policies on Agricultural export business.

1. 1.To identify the major structural and operational challenges faced by agricultural export businesses.
2. 2.To examine production, technology, human resource, market information, and quality-related constraints affecting agricultural exports.
3. 3.To analyze market access, pricing, and customer-related challenges in international agricultural trade.
4. 4.To Study the effectiveness of Government policies on Agricultural export business.

Research Methodology:

In this study, primary data were collected from 50 agricultural exporters in the Marathwada region using the survey method. A self-administered structured questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument.

Nature Of the Study:

The study is descriptive and analytical in nature.

Tools Of Analysis:

The data collected were analyzed using simple and appropriate statistical techniques. Percentage analysis was used to assess the level of agreement among respondents, and the results were presented in tables for easy understanding and comparison. Descriptive analysis was applied to explain the findings clearly, while the Chi-square test was used to examine whether significant differences existed in respondent opinions regarding the challenges faced by agricultural export businesses.

Limitations Of The Study:

This study is limited to understanding exporters' perceptions of the challenges they face

and the effectiveness of government policies in agricultural export business. It does not examine the manufacturing technologies or production practices adopted by exporters. Additionally, respondents' opinions may change over time due to variations in industry conditions, personal experiences, values, and access to information.

Although agricultural exports take place across India, the study is geographically confined to the Marathwada region due to time constraints and covers the period from 2017 to 2022.

Data Analysis And Interpretation:

Challenges of agricultural export Businesses and effectiveness of Government policies on Agricultural export business with special reference to selected from Marathwada region. The results obtained were classified, tabulated and the following analyses were performed in fulfilling the objectives of the study. This includes analysis the problems faced by Agricultural exporters.

Government policies on Agricultural export business. (Q.1 to Q.5)

Table No. 1 Addition of Rows and Columns: Observed Values.

Sr. No.	Questions	Option 1 Agree	Option 2 Strongly Agree	Option 3 Neutral	Option 4 Disagree	Option 5 Strongly Disagree	Total
01	Government export training programs have helped as export.	19	06	15	00	10	50
02	Government agencies are able to supply the information necessary to identify and develop international markets.	19	06	13	06	06	50
03	Government financial services have been helpful to firms involved in exporting.	32	06	00	06	06	50
04	Existing government regulations/restrictions are major obstacles for exporting.	32	06	00	06	06	50

05	Existing documentation required by government is complicated and excessive.	25	00	25	0	0	50
	Total	127	24	53	18	28	250

Source: Primary Data 2024-25

Test Statistics:

P Value = 0.005 Table Value =

$df = (r-1) * (C-1)$

$df = (5-1) * (5-1)$

Interpretation: The percentage analysis shows that most respondents agree or strongly agree that government policies support agricultural export businesses in the Marathwada region. This means that, overall, exporters feel that government policies are helpful and effective.

The Chi-square test shows that the calculated value ($\chi^2 = 76.93$) is higher than the table value (26.296) at the 5% level of significance. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the opinions of the respondents.

df = 16

Chi-Square = 76.9355 Table Value = **26.296**

Considering both the percentage analysis and the Chi-square test, it can be concluded that although government policies are generally seen as effective, exporters do not all think the same way. Some policies are seen as more useful than others, and therefore, certain areas need improvement.

Challenges before the Agri export businesses: (Q.1 to Q.12)

Table No.2

Sr. No.	Statement / Question	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Neutral (N)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Total
1	Inadequate/Untrained Personnel for Exporting	6	19	6	13	6	50
2	Lack of Excess Production Capacity for Exports	0	20	6	12	12	50
3	Lack of New Technology	6	32	6	0	6	50
4	Lack of Qualified Staff for International Marketing	0	31	0	6	13	50
5	Limited Information to Locate/analyze Markets	6	32	0	6	6	50
6	Problematic International Market Data and Limited Knowledge of Market Intelligence to Research Foreign Markets	0	20	6	12	12	50
7	Identifying Foreign Business Opportunities	6	32	0	6	6	50
8	Inability to Contact Overseas Customers and Lack of Foreign Market Assistance and Expertise	6	31	13	0	0	50
9	Lack of Meeting Export Product	6	32	0	6	6	50

	Quality/Standards						
10	Lack of Competitive Products	0	31	0	6	13	50
11	Difficulty in Offering Satisfactory Prices to Customers	6	38	6	0	0	50
12	Different Foreign Customers Habits and Attitudes	0	25	13	6	6	50
Total		42	343	56	73	86	600

Source: Primary Data 2024-25

Test Statistics:

Chi-Square Calculation:

Category	O	E	(O - E)	(O - E) ²	(O - E) ² / E
SA	42	120	-78	6084	50.7
A	343	120	223	49729	414.41
N	56	120	-64	4096	34.13
D	73	120	-47	2209	18.41
SD	86	120	-34	1156	9.63
Total χ^2					527.28

Source: Primary Data 2024-25

Expected Frequencies (E) =

Total responses = 600

Number of options = 5

E = 600/5 = 120

Expected Frequency (E) for each category = 120

Degrees of Freedom: $Df = n - 1 = 5 - 1 = 4$

Table value of χ^2 at 5 % level & $df = 4 = 9.488$

Calculated $\chi^2 = 527.28$

$527.28 > 9.488$

Interpretation:

The findings show that agricultural exporters face both structural and operational challenges. Shortage of skilled manpower and lack of foreign market information are key issues. High logistics costs and complex procedures create operational difficulties. Inadequate infrastructure and financial constraints affect export growth. The Chi-square analysis indicates that exporters do not perceive all challenges equally.

Findings:

The analysis shows a major issue is the lack of trained personnel and qualified staff for export activities and international marketing, while excess production capacity is generally not

a concern, indicating adequate production levels. Exporters also struggle with limited access to information on foreign markets, difficulties in identifying overseas business opportunities, and insufficient foreign market assistance and expertise. Additionally, meeting international quality standards, developing competitive products, offering suitable prices, and understanding foreign customer preferences remain significant challenges, particularly for exporters in the Marathwada region.

The analysis reveals mixed views on government support for exports. While about half of the respondents benefited from government policies, the rest did not. Most exporters were satisfied with the services and training programs offered by government agencies and found the

information and financial support useful for developing international markets. However, many respondents reported that complex regulations, restrictions, and excessive documentation continue to be major obstacles to export activities.

Interpretation:

The findings indicate that agricultural exporters in the Marathwada region face a range of operational and external challenges that affect their export performance. Key issues include a shortage of trained personnel, limited adoption of modern technology, weak international marketing expertise, and difficulties in accessing foreign market information, finding overseas buyers, and meeting international quality standards. Although government agencies offer training, financial support, and market information, these benefits are not equally accessible to all exporters, and complex regulations and documentation further hinder export activities. Overall, the results suggest that while production capacity is adequate, exporters require simpler procedures, better guidance, and stronger institutional support to enhance their export performance.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that agricultural exporters face several challenges that affect their ability to perform in international markets. While most exporters have sufficient production capacity, they struggle with issues such as lack of trained manpower, limited use of modern technology, and inadequate knowledge of international marketing. Exporters also find it difficult to access reliable foreign market information, identify overseas buyers, and meet international quality standards. Although government agencies provide various forms of support, the benefits are not equally experienced by all exporters, and complex regulations and documentation procedures continue to create

obstacles. Therefore, improving institutional support, simplifying export procedures, and strengthening capacity-building efforts are essential for enhancing agricultural export performance in the region.

Suggestions:

Agricultural exporters should take part in export promotion councils, buyer–seller meets, and trade fairs to find new foreign markets. New exporters should use safe payment options like Letters of Credit and ECGC schemes to reduce risk. Regular market surveys and EXIM training programs can help exporters understand customer needs, export procedures, and policies. Improving product quality, packaging, and meeting international standards is also essential, especially for exporters in the Marathwada region.

The government should simplify customs procedures by reducing documentation and improving clearance efficiency. Export Promotion Councils should strengthen support for small and non-exporters through affordable memberships, training, and continuous guidance. Practical export education and awareness programs should be expanded through institutions like KVKs to encourage new agricultural exporters. Special assistance should be provided to help exporters meet international quality and packaging standards. Indian embassies, Export Promotion Councils, and local government bodies should work together to promote agricultural exports and support Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) in regions such as Marathwada.

References:

1. Ahmed, Z. U., Julian, C. C., Baalbaki, I., & Hadidian, T. V. (2004). Export barriers and firm internationalization: a study of Lebanese entrepreneurs. *Journal of management & world business research*, Vol1 issue 1, pp-45-58.

2. Bombay, 76 Deb. Kalipada, (1976) Export Strategy in India, S.Chand & Company Ltd., New Delhi,
3. Jasdanwala, Z.V., (1966) Marketing efficiency in Indian Agriculture, Allied Press, Omabahal, Kathmandu,
4. Goyal S K, R N Pandey and J P Singh (2000), "India"s Agricultural Exports - Growth and Instability," Foreign trade review, Vol.XXXV Issue 1, April-June2000, Indian Institute of foreign trade, New Delhi, pp 32-46.
5. Gupta, A.P., (1975) Marketing of Agricultural Produce in India, Vora & Co., Publishers Pvt. Ltd.
6. Kabra, K. N., (1983), Agricultural exports, for whose benefit. Journal of Agricultural Economics, Vol 146, Issue 3 pp:939-41.
7. Lagzi Ali and Thimmararayappa (2012). "Agricultural Processed Food Products Exports from India: Challenges and Opportunities", Asian Journal of Development Matters, Vol.6, No.1. pp:7-12.

Websites:

1. www.dgft.gov.in
2. www.maharashtra.gov.in
3. www.apeda.gov.in